

DigiVet: Digitalisation of livestock data to improve veterinary public health

SWEDISH workshop report

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Contents

Executive Summary.....	4
Overview of the DigiVet Project.....	4
Introduction	5
Exercise 1 Challenges to the use and digitalization of AMU data.....	6
Introduction to DigiVet tools – AMView.....	11
Comments following trial of AMView.....	12
Estonia.....	12
Denmark.....	12
Norway.....	13
Sweden.....	13
UK.....	14
Lecture on different units used in AMU data.	18
APPENDIX 1- Participant affiliations:	19
Estonia.....	19
Denmark.....	19
Norway.....	19
Sweden.....	19
UK.....	19
APPENDIX 2 DigiVet project partners and contact details.....	20
APPENDIX 3 Overview of the current AMU data landscape/system in Denmark, Sweden and the UK.....	21
Denmark.....	21
Governance.....	21
Surveillance and Data-sharing	21
Estonia.....	21
Governance.....	21
Surveillance and Data-sharing	21
Norway.....	21
Governance.....	21
Surveillance and Data sharing.....	22
Sweden.....	22
Governance.....	22
Surveillance and Data-sharing	23

UK..... 23
 Governance..... 23
 Surveillance and Data-sharing 23

Executive Summary

The DigiVet project is studying how livestock data is currently used across the partner nations (Denmark, Estonia, Norway, Sweden and UK) and how technology, training, and regulatory frameworks might provide societal benefit by improving the public-interest uses of these data. As part of the project a workshop was held in Sweden to compare challenges in managing antimicrobial use (AMU) data across countries, present the AMView digitalisation tool and receive feedback on its utility from participants.

A total of 32 participants and project members from the 5 partner countries took part in the workshop in October 2023. There were some differences in how databases for recording AMU data are managed: in all countries except the UK, data is entered by vets and pharmacies, whereas in the UK this can also be done by farmers. Common challenges in data management and use were identified which were analysed through the framework of the data lifecycle (Zhang et al., 2022). These challenges included errors and gaps in data entry; incompatible entry formats which makes data aggregation difficult; legal frameworks creating challenges for data sharing; data quality limiting the use return value; limited return value for farmers in the use of the data and the sensitive nature of the data making stakeholders concerned about reputational risks to the agriculture industry from its use and the potential for supply chain actors to penalise farmers because of their use. A key difference between the countries was Denmark's relatively open policy in relation to AMU data, where data is more freely available to stakeholders than in other countries. Danish participants stated that there was now a level of trust in the system which allowed for data openness, though some difficulties over data sharing and use remained.

The project team gave a presentation about the AMView digitalisation tool and participants had an opportunity to trial the tool. Feedback on the tool included the need to present the data with a denominator to show relative use rather than total use per region. Participants identified different needs for different users and made suggestions about how the tool could meet these. This included farmers accessing their own data, and other anonymised data to allow for comparison and benchmarking. The potential for the tool to meet different reporting requirements was discussed. Participants wanted to ensure that data was treated with sensitivity and that appropriate restrictions were in place to allow for access to the right data for the right people, with anonymised of data where appropriate.

The results of the workshop show that despite different data collection, management and use infrastructures, the countries were experiencing similar challenges in relation to data digitalisation. Certain challenges could be partly addressed by a well-designed data digitalisation tool, though there was a perception that the needs of different actors should be addressed separately, including restricted access because of the sensitivity of AMU data.

Overview of the DigiVet Project

https://www.dcs.gla.ac.uk/~jenright/digivet_website/index.html

Successful management of livestock disease ensures a consistent supply of safe food for everyone in society. The use of data by industry, public services, and even the public at large is a key part of this veterinary public health mission. However, managing this data comes with many challenges: how should data collection be standardised, and who should have access to different aspects of this data? What risks are farmers exposed to by making their data publicly available? What data and

processes need to be maintained to be able to effectively control shared threats to our supply of safe food within our increasingly international society?

The DigiVet project is studying how livestock data is currently used across the partner nations (Denmark, Estonia, Norway, Sweden and UK) and how technology, training, and regulatory frameworks might provide societal benefit by improving the public-interest uses of these data. The study includes workshops with stakeholders to map existing practices, and document the gaps, roadblocks, and opportunities for improvement.

Three case studies will cover foodborne disease, antimicrobial usage, and contagious diseases of livestock. Foodborne illnesses such as Salmonella are a serious public health issue, antimicrobial usage in livestock may be contributing to the developing antimicrobial resistance problem in human pathogens. Exotic and highly contagious livestock diseases such as African swine fever have the potential to devastate our national agricultural sectors. Each of these challenges has wide-reaching implications for society as a whole.

Meeting these challenges requires different approaches, but each are united by their dependence on similar sources of data to enable authorities to continually monitor the threat and respond quickly when required. Within the study we test the models and statistical data analytics that are used in each partner nation across the other geographic settings, investigating what approaches will work under which circumstances, and what needs to change to facilitate more effective use of the data.

DigiVet will also investigate the risks associated with missing, sparse, or coarsely aggregated data, and evaluate the potential societal benefits of making better quality data more widely available.

The project is funded by Nordforsk, a body which funds Nordic research and cooperation:

<https://www.nordforsk.org/>.

Introduction

The final workshop of the DigiVet project was held in Uppsala, Sweden with the aim of facilitating discussion and co-learning among the stakeholders present about the digitalisation of AMU data and obtaining feedback on the AMView tool developed as part of the DigiVet project.

Participants from Denmark, Estonia, Norway, Sweden and the UK presented an overview of the management of antimicrobial use data in their countries and participants discussed the challenges in the use and digitalization of AMU data. They also gave feedback in breakout groups on a new digitalisation tool, AMView which was developed by Swedish partners in the DigiVet project.

The workshop was attended by 22 key stakeholders from Denmark, Estonia, Norway, Sweden and UK, and 10 of the DigiVet project team. Members of the DigiVet project team facilitated the discussions, presented on the AMView app and several took part in the breakout group discussions. The participants' affiliations can be found in Appendix 1 and partner contact details in Appendix 2. A brief summary of the current AMU data landscape/system in the 5 countries can be found in Appendix 3. All participants were asked to read an information sheet and sign a consent form prior to the start of the workshop.

Exercise 1 Challenges to the use and digitalization of AMU data

In all countries except the UK, data on AMU is entered by vets and pharmacies, whereas in the UK, both vets and farmers can enter data in the Agriculture and Horticulture Development Board (AHDB) cattle database. Databases were managed either in-house by the organisation tasked with the production and management of an AMU database, such as the AHDB in the UK, or outsourced to an external company as was the case in Denmark. Participants reported a number of similar challenges in the use and digitalisation of AMU data in each country.

The data is presented according to the data lifecycle theoretical framework, adapted from Zhang et al. (2022)¹ in relation to human health data, as can be seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Data lifecycle taken from Zhang et al. (2022)

There was concern around the quality of reported data, for instance data not being updated or missing altogether, and manual steps leading to human error making it difficult to draw accurate conclusions. Units of use and denominators differ across datasets making comparative assessments difficult. Furthermore, identifying the active ingredient in medicines is problematic as databases may allow free text entries resulting in the product trade name rather than the active ingredient being entered.

Legal frameworks can be challenging and GDPR and ownership of data is a concern in some countries. In Denmark all data are publicly available and there is now an element of trust in the system. But stakeholders from other countries expressed concern about how data records would be used and distributed and if they would lead to penalties for farmers. AMU is a "pre-competitive issue" in the UK, meaning that retailers and other supply chain actors do not market their produce

¹ Zhang, J., Symons, J., Agapow, P., Teo, J.T., Paxton, C.A., Abdi, J., Mattie, H., Davie, C., Torres, A.Z., Folarin, A., Sood, H., Celi, L.A., Halamka, J., Eapen, S., & Budhdeo, S. (2022) Best practices in the real-world data life cycle. *PLOS Digital Health*, 1(1), e0000003. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pdig.0000003>

based on levels of AMU and so AMU data is not used to gain a competitive advantage in the marketplace, which was seen as a strength.

Although in some countries it is compulsory for vets to enter data, not all will comply, and engaging farmers in the process was also seen as difficult. Though the collaborative involvement of farmers in the database was seen as positive in the UK. There was also some discussion about how to achieve the benchmark figure and whether vets and farmers should be benchmarked at all. Further details can be found in table 1 below.

Table 1 Challenge for data use and digitalisation

	Country Data Acquisition (connectivity, wearables, electronic group identification, decision-support tools, diagnostics etc.)	Data Aggregation and Enrichment (data handling, interoperability, harmonisation etc.)	Data Management and Maintenance (partitioning, access, security etc.)	Data Usage and Return Value (Costs, relevance, user-friendliness, trust, transparency etc)
UK	<p>The quality of data entry is variable: there is missing data, human error in data entry, and data not being updated.</p> <p>Difficulties engaging farmers to enter AMU data into the AHDB cattle database.</p>	<p>Vet practices' management systems have many different sources which are difficult to pool and combine.</p> <p>Identifying the active ingredient in a medicine may be challenging if medicines are entered via free text.</p> <p>Data may be entered using different units making them difficult to combine.</p> <p>Currently there is good data on AMU sales but data on the use of these medicines is not complete.</p>	<p>Navigating legal frameworks to allow for data sharing is challenging.</p> <p>Producing data sharing agreements is difficult and time consuming.</p> <p>Building and maintaining a database in-house was challenging.</p>	<p>Farmer fear over the potential of data to be used by retailers and other actors to penalise them.</p> <p>Data could be better used for benchmarking.</p> <p>Currently AMU data has a low return value for farmers.</p> <p>It can be difficult to publish data while ensuring that it will be interpreted and understood within the right context.</p> <p>Data holders feel responsible for the use of any published data.</p> <p>It could be made easier for farmers to give consent for the use of their data.</p> <p>The variable quality of data limits its current usefulness in some sectors.</p>

Norway	<p>The quality of data entry is variable: there is missing data, human error in data entry, and data not being updated.</p>	<p>Data may be entered and stored in different formats making it difficult to integrate them.</p> <p>Data may be entered using different units making them difficult to combine.</p>	<p>The data are stored on an old system where it can be difficult to make changes.</p> <p>There is an effective legal framework in place for data sharing, but there are still problems posed by GDPR regulations.</p>	<p>Norway has a system for recording AMU but the vision for its use is not clear.</p>
Denmark	<p>Data on number of animals per farm may not be accurate as it may relate to the maximum number of animals that can be kept on the farm rather than the actual number of animals present on the farm.</p> <p>Data on prescriptions may not be accurate because vets may advise farmers to use medications differently to the summary product characteristics to avoid the farm being given a “yellow card” for high AMU.</p> <p>The input of very detailed data leads to mistakes in data entry.</p>			<p>There are political barriers to using the data that exists, it’s difficult to communicate advanced information.</p> <p>In using data for veterinarians benchmarking, it’s difficult to define what the benchmark should be.</p> <p>Politicians are having difficulty understanding new methods to join data as they are used to seeing data presented in a particular way.</p> <p>It is desirable to make a dashboard and benchmarking to improve reporting of data, but this requires resources.</p>
Estonia	<p>The quality of data entry is variable: there is missing data, human error in data entry, and data not being updated.</p> <p>Not all vets input data even though it is compulsory.</p>	<p>Connecting data on sales and use is an issue.</p>	<p>Navigating legal frameworks to allow for data sharing between institutions is challenging.</p>	<p>Estonia’s AMU database is new and has not produced outputs as yet.</p> <p>Data quality issues in Estonia make effective use challenging.</p>

Sweden	For the antimicrobial use data, the quality of data entry is variable: there is missing data, human error in data entry, and data not being updated.	Data may be entered using different units making them difficult to integrate.	<p>Navigating legal frameworks to allow for data sharing is challenging.</p> <p>The previous system did not have a good enough quality to retrieve AMU data for all food producing animal species, but dairy cattle. (To comply with the mandatory reporting, a new system has been developed and introduced in 2023, which needs further work of refinement and also addition of more animal species.)</p>	<p>There's a challenge in creating a comparative system for benchmarking.</p> <p>How can farmers be encouraged to be interested in the data and ask for access to the data?</p>
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Introduction to DigiVet tools – AMView

AMView is an R Shiny application that visualizes AMU data in animals. Once data is formatted into the common AMU data structure, which has been developed within the project, AMView visualises the data in two views: Trends (Figure 2) and Maps (Figure 3), with various filtering and grouping options. In the presentation of AMView, the background of the dashboard development and a practical example of how AMView can be populated by real-world data was presented with a Norwegian case. For the showcase of AMView at the workshop, artificial data was used which was generated based on official AMU statistics from the Swedish cattle sector. The feature to generate artificial data is built into AMView and can be customised to the user's needs.

Figure 2 Trends page of AMView

Figure 3 Map page of AMView

Comments following trial of AMView

Participants were given the opportunity to familiarise themselves with the tool in country groups, and comments were captured.

Estonia

Stakeholders from Estonia thought the tool could be highly beneficial. They felt that visualization and the ability to compare the data must be the purpose of the data collection, which AMView provides.

They liked the idea of transparency and that the tool would be accessible to everybody via the web or an app. It allows the stakeholders to see the actual benefits of data collection and reporting. They thought it was important to review the legal aspects and liked the option of certain restrictions on the information that can be released to the public. They felt that the main problem remains with the validity and quality of the data. It is important to be sure that the information is valid in order to make it available to stakeholders. With certain data, the program could be more individualized (e.g., regions, local authority unit, etc.).

Denmark

Stakeholders from Denmark wondered who the tool was targeted at. They thought it was too complicated for the public, but farmers and vets would be interested if they can see their own data. They thought it should start on the map page with filtered data e.g., medicine groups and maybe use symbols or images of animals in the presentation. The option of a bar versus a line chart is good and being able to target output to a specific audience is useful.

There is missing denominator data which could be slaughter data in numbers or weight for example, and there needs to be an option to select dose or number of treatments. The addition of a

treatment route (oral, injection) as a filter could be useful. The stakeholders thought that grouping by date or day was not the most helpful way to present it, but that data could be aggregated to a month for example, depending on the date range.

They thought farmers would like it if they can see their own farm data, particularly if they can also see other data e.g., milk deliveries, somatic cell counts etc. Being able to log in to personal data via e.g., MitID in Denmark, would be useful. In addition, being able to compare their own region with others as a benchmark and adjust the spatial resolution of the map while employing spatial anonymization, if necessary, could be an advantage. However, they thought the scope of the tool was too wide and needs to be more focussed.

Norway

This dashboard can be useful to present statistics and for stakeholders. They evaluated the dashboard on the condition that the aim is to present aggregated information. They did not expect that it should cover needs for reports on AMU for single farmers or veterinary practitioners.

They thought it should be possible to generate the reports needed for the European Medicines Agency (EMA) to ensure that it is the exact same figures from the dashboard as are sent to EMA. Therefore, the variable package size for medicine products will be required as this should be reported to EMA.

In addition to kg, it would be useful to include mg per PCU². The European Surveillance of Veterinary Antimicrobial Consumption (ESVAC) has a standard definition for this that can be implemented into the app.

Norwegian stakeholders would like to be able to report the data both on

- County at NUTS3 (Nomenclature of territorial units for statistics) level and
- NFSA (Norwegian Food Safety Authorities) regions.

The NFSA regions are larger than NUTS3 but are not the same as NUTS2.

They envisaged a potential problem if there are few medicine producers that sell an antibiotic in the Norwegian market. There may be that a group of antimicrobial agents that are sold by a single provider only. They are uncertain that they can display the use of those for confidentiality reasons.

There was an enquiry whether the app could be modified so that detailed information is available for some groups (after log-on), but not available for the general public. For example, information on NUTS3, and whether it would be possible to include whole sales data.

Other comments included whether it is possible to upload the data to the app without the requirement to install the package again, and will the app be able to handle gigabytes (GBs) of data.

Sweden

Swedish stakeholders gave the following suggestions for further development.

² The mg/PCU (population correction unit) is a unit of measurement developed by the European Medicines Agency to monitor antibiotic use and sales across Europe,

It was stated that this is sensitive information which needs to be considered in relation to accessibility.

The ability to see data at a veterinary level, and workplace/clinic level would be useful, which could be restricted to the appropriate people through the requirement for a log in to access. It was stated that filtering on species- and species-specific diagrams would be useful. Showing results per batch would be of interest to pig and poultry farmers. There was an enquiry whether there are enough variables in the data, or do new variables need to be added.

Stakeholders stated that the tool could be further adapted to the user; what do farmers need/want to see? Växa has seen different levels of interest from farmers in different sectors. It could be useful to ask farmers directly about their needs. Return value for different users is important to identify - people like to know 'what's in it for me'.

Växa is making reports on what antibiotics are used for which feeds back to advisors and recommendations, but they do not use AMU data in this way. There may also be other users who could be asked for input. The app could be made accessible from a platform the user is already using such as Kokontrollen, MinGård or WinPig.

Comparisons to average, median, percentiles would be useful, but only presenting use in kg is not enough. Systems for sharing data will be necessary and it is important that it is user friendly, i.e. filters can be saved for individual users. Validation of data will be important for engendering trust and usefulness.

UK

Stakeholders from the UK thought the tool was a quick, easy, efficient way of reporting AMU and was intuitive and manipulatable, but they were unsure of its purpose. It may be useful for policy makers and individual farmers, as a 'One Health' tool or a public educational tool. AMU in the agriculture sector is a sensitive topic and care needs to be taken about how and to whom data on agriculture AMU is presented. There was concern about the metric: it was suggested there should be a denominator in the data to show AMU per animal rather than total AMU per region, as this would provide more valuable information to the industry and government. But it would need to be more relevant to the UK now as there was no information included in the app that the UK does not already have.

Participants thought it was useful to have a filter for high priority critically important antibiotics (HPCIA) and a 'reason for treatment' filter.

The UK is working on developing a companion animal dataset. This tool could be a useful dashboard for that and could bridge the gap for the new reporting group.

The feedback is summarised in table 3.

Table 3 Feedback on the use of the AMView tool for visualising AMU data

Breakout group	Data Aquisition (connectivity, wearables, electronic identification, decision-support tools, diagnostics etc.)	Data Aggregation and Enrichment (data handling, interoperability, harmonisation etc.)	Data Management and Maintenance (partitioning, access, security etc.)	Data Usage and Return Value (Costs, relevance, user-friendliness, trust, transparency etc)
UK		<p>The data needs to be presented with a denominator to show relative AMU, rather than aggregate AMU per region.</p> <p>Additional functionality could be added to make the tool more useful, such as showing the use of high priority critically important antibiotics, showing surveillance data on AMR and/or a 'reason for treatment' list attached to the AMU data.</p>		<p>The tool was intuitive and easy to use.</p> <p>Additional functionality could be added to make the tool more useful, such as showing the use of high priority critically important antibiotics, showing surveillance data on AMR and/or a 'reason for treatment' list attached to the AMU data.</p> <p>It could be useful to make the tool a one health application that presents AMU data from different sectors, including human medicine and companion animal for educating the public about AMU.</p> <p>AMU in the agriculture sector is a sensitive topic and care needs to be taken about how and to whom data on agricultural AMU is presented.</p>
Norway		<p>It would be useful to include a denominator in the data, such as population correction unit.</p> <p>Queries were made about how much data the app could process and how to upload data to the app.</p>	<p>Access to data about AMU in specific locations needs to be treated carefully and only made available to relevant actors.</p>	<p>The app could use different systems for designating regions which are used in different reporting frameworks.</p> <p>The app could be modified to show different scales of information to different actors, with smaller scale, more sensitive information only available to specific actors.</p>

			<p>In its current iteration, the app will not fulfil AMU reporting requirements for farmers and vets.</p> <p>Data in the app could be used to generate reports on AMU for the European Medicines Agency.</p>
Denmark	<p>It would be useful to include a denominator in the data.</p> <p>There could be more options for filtering data, such as by animal species, age group within a species, medicine group, dose and number of treatments, treatment route, and presenting the data over a different time period such as a week.</p>		<p>Providing different visualisation options such as a bar or line chart is useful.</p> <p>It would be useful to be able to adjust the spatial resolution of the map, while keeping spatial anonymisation.</p> <p>The app has potential return value for farmers, if they can access their own data, along with other metrics about their farm.</p>
Estonia		<p>There should be restrictions on what data is accessible to whom.</p>	<p>The data could be presented at different scales to make it more relevant to specific users, with appropriate restrictions on access.</p> <p>Data visualisation is useful and has the potential to compare AMU data across time scales and regions.</p> <p>The app could improve transparency and allow stakeholders to view AMU data.</p>

			<p>The quality of the data limits the app's usefulness in providing outputs for stakeholders.</p>
Sweden	<p>Data could be filtered by species.</p> <p>Data should be presented with a denominator to show relative use.</p>	<p>Access to data about AMU in specific locations needs to be treated carefully and only made available to relevant actors.</p>	<p>If data was presented by veterinary practice or clinic this would provide useful information, as long as access was restricted to appropriate people.</p> <p>The visualisation app could be integrated with existing platforms stakeholders use for recording AMU and other production parameters.</p> <p>The app could be adapted to share data between relevant parties.</p> <p>Data on AMU is sensitive, and care needs to be taken in relation to accessibility of the data.</p> <p>The return value of the tool will be different for different audiences. The data presented could be adapted to what is relevant to farmers.</p>

Lecture on different units used in AMU data.

“Why is Choosing how to Report Antimicrobial Use so challenging?”

Following the presentation by Carolee Carson & Angelina Bosman at PHAC/ASPC in Canada, participants had a short discussion in plenary. Participants stated that one size will not fit all in choosing metrics to describe and represent AMU and that it is hard to find a standardised approach. In comparisons across countries, metrics may be chosen strategically that shows a country in the best light. Each country should set up a system that’s best for them. It’s better to compare within and not between countries and to think about what makes sense in that country. There is no requirement that data be harmonised and standardised between countries. However, comparisons between countries will be made to stake market advantage or to drive the debate in some countries.

Next step

Based on the feedback at the workshop, some minor changes will be made to AMView to be delivered for the project. Further development work is planned and will be shared with the stakeholders when it is put on the public repository (GitHub) as a package.

APPENDIX 1- Participant affiliations:

Estonia: Four female stakeholders participated from Estonia.

- Two from the Agriculture and Food Board
- One from the National Centre for Laboratory Research and Risk Assessment (LABRIS)
- One from the Ministry of Regional Affairs

Denmark: Three female stakeholders participated from Denmark.

- One from the Danish Veterinary and Food Administration (FVST)
- One from the Technical University of Denmark (DTU)
- One from the Danish Agriculture and Food Council (DAFC)

Norway: Three stakeholders participated from Norway, two female and one male.

- Two from the Norwegian Veterinary Institute
- One from the Norwegian Food Safety Authority

Sweden: Six stakeholders participated from Sweden, four female and two male.

- Three from the Swedish National Veterinary Institute (SVA)
- One from Växa Sverige
- One from Gård & Djurhälsan (Farm & Animal Health)
- One from the Swedish Board of Agriculture

UK: Six stakeholders participated from the UK, four female and two male.

- One from the Agriculture and Horticulture Development Board (AHDB)
- Two from the Veterinary Medicines Directorate (VMD)
- Two from Responsible Use of Medicines in Agriculture Alliance (RUMA)
- One from the National Farmers Union (NFU)

APPENDIX 2 DigiVet project partners and contact details

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APPENDIX 3 Overview of the current AMU data landscape/system in Denmark, Sweden and the UK.

Denmark

Governance

Complementary to the EU regulation (2019/6 (EU) a Danish regulation exists. This is the law on medicinal products (LBK 99, 2018), which covers production, market authorisation and distribution (including packaging) of medicinal products for both humans and animals; it covers more or less all products and the entire chain from producers to patients (including animals).

Surveillance and Data-sharing

All antimicrobial usage on farm-level is reported to VetStat, which is the Danish Veterinary and Food Administration database on authorised veterinarians, practices, veterinary advisory service contracts and consumption of veterinary medicines and coccidiostats in Denmark.

Estonia

Governance

The Estonian legislation regulating the production, authorisation and use of antimicrobials (complimenting the EU regulation 2019/6) includes [Medicinal Products Act](#), which regulates, production, market authorisation and distribution of medicinal products for humans and animals, and the Veterinary act, that regulates the use and reporting of the use of medicinal products, including antimicrobials, by veterinarians. The detailed provisions on the use and reporting are enacted with the regulations of the minister of regions and agriculture (formerly minister of rural affaires or minister of agriculture). The antimicrobial drugs are “prescription only medicines” in Estonia. The farmers can administer the antimicrobials as prescribed and under the supervision of the veterinarian.

Surveillance and Data-sharing

The records on usage of antimicrobials in farms was recorded until recently only in farm records and inspected by veterinary authorities at farm inspections. Since 2023 the usage is also recorded in central database held by the veterinary authority - the Board of Agriculture and Food. In addition to the usage in farm animals the usage in pets and other categories of animals is recorded in this database.

Norway

Governance

"Regulation (EU) 2019/6 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 December 2018 on veterinary medicinal products and repealing Directive 2001/82/EC" is implemented in Norwegian law in accord with "EØS-avtalen – Vedlegg II Tekniske forskrifter, standarder, prøving og sertifisering", chapter XIII. Legemidler. In addition, there are national regulations.

Law on medicinal products (LOV-1992-12-04-132), which covers production, market authorisation and distribution (including packaging) of medicinal products for both humans and animals. Concerning animals, only parts not covered by Regulation (EU) 2019/6 is relevant. The law on veterinarians and other animal health personnel (LOV-2001-06-15-75) and the law on food

production and food safety etc. (LOV-2003-12-19-124) includes, among others, requirements for the veterinarians regarding AMU.

In general, only authorised veterinarians are allowed to prescribe antimicrobials and in addition authorised fish biologists can prescribe antimicrobials to aquaculture. Veterinarians cannot sell medicines to animal owners unless needed for treatment before the medicines could have been purchased from a pharmacy. Furthermore, the veterinarians are not allowed to make profit when selling medicines: medicines must be sold to self-cost.

Veterinarians are required to keep a record of all treatments and report all use of medicines in production animals to the authorities. The pharmacies should report all prescriptions for animals to the authorities.

An important point in the prescription of any product is the cascade rule described in Articles 112, 113 and 114 of Regulation (EU) 2019/6.

1. choosing a product approved in Norway or EU for specific animal species and indication; otherwise,
2. choosing a product approved for another animal species or indication; otherwise,
3. choosing a product approved for humans or a product approved in another country (and subsequently also on delivery agreement from the Norwegian Medicines Agency); otherwise,
4. magistral preparation of a medicinal product, based on derogation from the Norwegian Food Safety Authority, if the product is not listed.

Surveillance and Data sharing

The Norwegian Veterinary Prescription register includes information on sale and use of medicines to animals. It covers

- all sales of medicines from pharmacies to veterinarians,
- all prescriptions delivered from pharmacies to end users,
- all usage of medicines in production animals (including aquaculture).

The Norwegian Veterinary Prescription register is owned by the Norwegian Food Safety Authority. For each record, the register comprises information on date of sale or usage, pharmacy, veterinarian, animal owner and or herd ID (if production animal), animal category, indication for usage, medicine and amount used, treatment length, withdrawal period.

The Norwegian Food Safety Authority and the Norwegian Veterinary Institute has a data sharing agreement that gives the Norwegian Veterinary Institute access to information in the Veterinary Prescription Register for purposes related to governmental support.

Sweden

Governance

In addition to Regulations (EU) 2019/6 and 2019/4, there are also Swedish regulations on the sales and use of antimicrobials. According to Regulation (EU) 2019/6, veterinary medicinal products with antimicrobials are “prescription only medicines”. In Sweden, only pharmacies may sell veterinary medicinal products to end users. Animal owners and veterinarians buying for use in own practice

(requisitions) are considered as end users. All pharmacies are obliged to report all sales of medicinal products to the eHealth Agency (SFS 2009:659 as amended by 2021:130). The regulations SFS 2021:1129 and SFS 2021:1132 control how information and data on sales of medicinal products for animals are registered at the eHealth Agency and shared to some other parts, such as the Swedish Board of Agriculture (SBA) and the Swedish National Veterinary Institute (SVA). Development and further improvement of a new system to collect the antibiotic use data is under way by the SBA.

Surveillance and Data-sharing

Data that is currently shared by the eHealth Agency to SVA and SBA is confidential and protected according to law SFS 2009:400 and regulation SFS 2009:641 as amended.

Sales of antimicrobials from pharmacies: The Swedish eHealth Agency maintains the register of pharmaceutical sales (FOTA). Veterinary medicinal products are sold at pharmacies, either directly to animal owners with prescriptions from veterinarians or to veterinarians (requisition for use in own practice). Sales on distance, only when it is by prescription, is allowed, both to animal owners and to veterinarians.

UK

Governance

In the UK, the use of antimicrobials in farm animals is regulated by the Veterinary Medicines Regulation 2013. This covers the manufacture, supply, sale and use of antimicrobials. Antimicrobials can only be prescribed by a veterinarian when the animal is under the veterinarian's care and when they have carried out a clinical assessment of the animal. Following Brexit, imports of pharmaceuticals from the EU to the UK must receive authorisation as of June 2021.

The Veterinary Medicines Directorate (VMD) is the executive agency of the Department of Environment, Food and Rural Affairs (Defra), which is responsible for enforcing legislation, monitoring the sale of antimicrobials and antimicrobial (AM) resistance, and advising government ministers on updating AM policy. The VMD operates across the 4 countries in the UK.

The UK will not implement Regulations (EU) 2019/4 and 2019/6 following their exit from the European Union in 2020. The UK government will carry out a public consultation on changing the UK's laws on antimicrobial use, including consideration of the new EU rules.

Surveillance and Data-sharing.

The VMD publish annual reports on antimicrobial usage data from some sectors as well as sales data (VARSS Annual Report). Many antimicrobials are authorised for use in several animal species, so it is difficult to get an accurate picture of use by animal species from sales data alone. The VMD works with livestock sectors to gather use data for different species.

The AHDB already record usage from pigs, poultry and aquaculture sectors, and launched an online Medicine Hub in January 2021 which aims to appeal to beef and dairy individual farms to input their antimicrobial use data so they can track and benchmark their own use. The Medicines Hub also aims to import data from other sources such as farm software and veterinary practices. The ultimate aim is to link the Medicine Hub data with national compulsory animal traceability systems and to use the data in the VMD annual report.